

THE HISTORY OF ORIGIN OF DRABBLES UZBEK AND ENGLISH LITERATURE

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Abstract: In Uzbek and English literature, **drabbles** are a relatively new **genre** in modern **literature**. This article discusses the significance, purpose, and **history** of this genre. We all know that the study of literature is a fascinating and expanding field. As a result, there have been numerous advancements and changes in this **field**. It can be asserted that the development of drabbles is not an ancient history. The article focuses on deep an analysis of drabbles, which are **short stories** of less than 100 words that date back to 1980. According to the analysis of drabbles in both languages' literature, drabbles originated in **English literature**, moved to **Uzbek literature**, and still evolving today. The drabble genre demands more effort from the writer due to its intricacy compared to the **narrative genre**. The reason is that a writer only needs story writing skill to convey a **story** in just 100 words. Nevertheless, well-known **authors** of stories in both Uzbek and English eventually experimented with drabble and gained success. In addition, this article examines well-known drabble authors and their **creations**.

Key words: Drabbles, genre, literature, history, field, short story, English literature, Uzbek literature, narrative genre, story, authors, creations.

Introduction

As we know, today the most fields in the world are developing day by day for instance, in literary studies a number of changes and development are happening.

The formal and substantive advancement of Uzbek and international literature produces original innovations and offers readers engrossing and perceptive works. Additionally, literary communication advances genre studies and helps writers and readers conform to modern standards. Specifically, the story genre is evolving and entering new phrases. The genre of stories is broad and has many different classifications. We can find the writings of numerous well-known authors in the narrative genre, along with their perspectives on it.

Literary studies, both international and Uzbek, have extensively examined the distinctive features of the story genre. Regarding the story genre, for instance, Norwegian literary critic Juan Rulfo stated, "I think the story is a more difficult and responsible genre than the novel"¹. This concept highlights the duties of a small work and the weight put on the narrative genre. Because of its intricacy and uniqueness from other genres, the narrative genre demands a great deal of creativity from its writers. However, stories that deviate from the narrative genre which has grown in popularity among writers are also emerging in recent years.

In both Uzbek and English literature stories are getting shorter, which motivates writers to improve their story creation skills. As we know there is not any kind of size restriction when writing a novel or story, so the authors can freely show their deep feelings. *Kichik hikoyalar ingliz tilida "flash fiction" deb nomlanib, bu hajman juda qisqa badiiy asar hisoblanadi.* Many views on the characteristics of short stories and their categories have been expressed in various places. Particularly, some works that focus on the needs of the rapidly evolving social networks of today are assessed as "a story with a total length of 280 characters (known as "Twitterature" because it is the most characters that can be posted on the social media platform Twitter)"². These cases are different, though, in that they do not rely on literary theories. According to another viewpoint on short stories "dribble is also short story however it includes only 50 words"³. This theoretical perspective is unique in that it departs from the conventions that are widely acknowledge among literary scholars. "Sudden fiction" is defined as stories that are no longer than 750 words.⁴

Furthermore, the genre requirements of the small-scale dwarf story we are examining are not met by this point of view. One kind of story is called a "micro story", and it has 1000 words.⁵ These divergent viewpoints on short stories can be understood as phases in the evolution of short works. For

Y.Solijonov . Hozirgi adabiy jarayon: o'quv qo'llanma.-T.: Innovatsion ziyo, 2020. - bet 63

² Maddie Crum ["Twitter Fiction Reveals. The Power of Very, Very Short Stories"](#). *The Huffington Post*. (May 7, 2015).

³ Graham ["Flash fiction - all you ever wanted to know, but were afraid to ask..."](#) *The Bridport Prize*. (March 8, 2013).

⁴ Becky Tuch. ["Flash Fiction: What's It All About?"](#). *The Review Review*. 2019-02-16

⁵ Christopher Kasparek, "Two Micro-Stories by Bolesław Prus", *The Polish Review*, 1995, no. 1, pp. 99-103.

instance, “drabbles are short stories that are shorter than 100 words”.⁶ Such perspectives and studies of the routes followed to arrive at a single form or conclusion will undoubtedly encourage the development of an ideal theory.

Materials and methods

Society is evolving and changing all the time. Psychological uniformity is disliked by the human mind. Thus, common to all art forms are their diversity and steady advancement. As a creative tool, literature coexists with these mechanisms. Within artistic works, alterations in structure, contents, and idea renewal are normal and consistent, indicating both a high degree of writers’ skill and the work’s level of perfection. Drabbles are one of the contemporary, emerging literary forms that require this kind of precision. Drabble began as a kind of narrative and evolved into its own direction. In world literary studies, drabbles have already developed into their own distinct genre. The narrative genre in literature is smaller in scope and expression than larger stories. The story stands out because its goal is to convey big ideas in brief visuals and expose big issues in a brief episode. In world literature, real ideas must be presented in brief forms within the predefined parameters of the narrative genre in order to expose significant issues. Drabble originated as a result of these actions. Their formation is influenced by folk art.

Writers of short stories ought to be able capture existing realities in a limited number of words. With their skill, writers ought to be able to condense significant events into a mere 100 words. For this reason, writing a short story is enjoyable and challenging at the same time. The number of authors producing short stories has been rising recently, despite the genre’s recent inception. Drabbles are the most popular kind of stories mentioned above. 20th century short stories are referred to as “drabble” in world literature. The English language gave rise to the word “drabble”, which means “ fragment”. “in 1971, Monty Python’s Big Red Book introduced the term drabble, describing it as a word game in which participants write novels.”⁷ There are different views regarding the origin of drabble, which is thought to be native to Great Britain. However, the drabble genre began to take shape in the 1980s. Drabble originated around this time as a result of a word game developed by University of Birmingham students. After that drabbles started showing up in newspaper texts. The “New Times” magazine’s founder, Steve Moss, established a short

⁶ Graham ["Flash fiction - all you ever wanted to know, but were afraid to ask..."](#) *The Bridport Prize*. (March 8, 2013).

⁷ <http://www.ansible.co.uk/writing/drabbles.html>

story competition in 1987 that had a significant impact on the global spread of drabbles. Writing drabbles is slowly expanding to other countries UK writers are required to write a brief piece of less than 100 words that includes a complete solution. Drabbles were mostly produced as a result of writing contests where participants had to produce 100 short pieces on a given subject over a certain period of time.

“Writers of short stories are compelled by the volume requirements to condense words and symbols in order to convey greater meaning, while readers are afforded the opportunity to appreciate the unique artistic example and experience awe”.⁸ Drabbles have several special features. For instance;

- It should cover the shortest and most comprehensive reality;
- It should end with an unexpected solution;
- It should provide a brief history of the reality.

“On the other hand, there are instances where short stories interpreted as mini-stories, or drabbles, rather than as a distinct genre in world literature”.⁹ However, the fact that these kinds of works have been published and that readers find them interesting is what matters most for the literary process. The structure and themes of these short stories are being studied by literary scholars.

“Dripping water” is a drabble by Aleksandr Sergeevich Neverov, the author of “Tashkent- the city of bread.” It explains that people should strive to do good in any circumstance using the example of a sparrow.

“Forest was burning. Once it reached the river, the sparrow carried the water in its mouth and flew into the forest. As the forest burned, one of the animals laughed and yelled;

- “Hey, will you save the forest with a drop of water?”
- what can I do, that’s all I can do, the sparrow said.”¹⁰

This drabble demonstrates the writer’s skill to us quite well. The reason is that this short piece combines three drabble traits. It contains the actual history expressed in the sentence “The forest was burning.” It’s common knowledge that history provides insight into the past. A forest fire is described in this sentence of this drabble. Why did the author decide to focus this drabble on the forest?

Жилина Л. В. Короче! Short-short story в современной японской литературе // Окно в Японию.

Драбблар. Duniyoning eng kichik hikoyalari. “O‘qituvchi nashriyot-matbaa ijodiy uyi”, 2018. — 6 б.

This is because the forest will experience terrible and strong fires. Additionally, this sentence describes reality as an extremely challenging situation in which all animals are helpless. The following line of the short story above is, “what can I do, that’s all I can do” is a succinct and complete reality. That’s because the author did not just randomly select the image of a sparrow attempting to put out a forest fire. The sparrow is the weakest of all the creatures in the forest, despite the presence of other strong animals. Through the use of contrasting symbols, the author of this drabble deftly conveys the idea that the sparrow can not simply observe the forest fire without taking action. Furthermore, despite the fact that there is a river close to the forest, providing a chance to put out the fire, all of the animals in it do nothing but watch their homes burn. An unexpected way to deal with reality is to try using a drop of water to put out a forest fire. Let’s focus more on the sparrow image as we examine this drabble. A sparrow can fly, so it can get away from any hazardous situation. He could fly out of the forest to escape a situation like that and save his life. Unlike other strong animals, he attempted to save his forest even though he was unable to leave his home. This drabble was created by Aleksandr Sergeevich Neverov, and its main concept is that humanity can come together in order to save the world in any challenging circumstance. Famous authors from around the world have written drabbles that draw attention because of their briefness. For instance, the English author Ernest Hemingway wrote a drabble that was just six words long.

“For sale: baby shoes, never worn”¹¹. All the traits of drabbles are evidents in this little piece, which appears straightforward but conceals a deep meaning. For instance , a brief history, an unexpected solution, and a brief reality are all provided. This drabble gives a brief history of the term “never worn.” The reader is attempting to understand the meaning behind the statement “unworn children’s shoes for sale” through this sentence. There are numerous reasons for this. For instance, there might be a sale on new shoes due to excess or necessity. However, a picture of a mother who lost her child and is selling the child’s shoes lies at the core of reality. In this drabble, the term “baby shoes” is an unexpected solution. The fact that the author used an image of a baby for this brief piece indicates that his drabble writing ability is quite well. This is because, in comparison to other characters, the baby’s character is surprisingly impressive. For example, if the drabble is “women’s shoes for sale that have never been worn”, any kind of reader will be excited or feel any emotion. The story’s

¹¹ Garson O'Toole "For Sale, Baby Shoes, Never Worn". quoteinvestigator.com. April 2013.

shortest and complete solution occurs when a mother who has lost her child in this drabble chooses to sell the unworn shoes of her deceased child. The reason is that a mother understands the agony of having her child stained, and she even sold her child's unused shoes to ease the pain. In other words, even though they are brief, short stories ought to be deeply meaningful.

Results and discussion

When we examine the history of world literature, we find that drabbles have emerged in many eras and nations and have continued to evolve to this day. Short stories were inspired by the story's genre. The reason for this is that writers have developed a strong interest in short stories. In recent years, most drabbles created by writers have made popular of this genre around the world. While the genre of drabbles started to develop and become popular worldwide in the 20th century, other genres that share drabble elements have been around for centuries. The impact of proverbs and anecdotes on the writing of short stories is easily discernible. All ancient nation's folklore contains these types of stories.¹²

Drabbles became prominent in world literature because of proverbs and anecdotes. The salient features of these genres is that proverbs' general conclusion are comparable to drabbles' descriptions of reality's endings. Furthermore, in terms of content the parable and short story genre are very similar. This is because the main aim of parables' is to achieve educational goal.¹³

"Uzbek literature from the 20th century is referred to as new Uzbek literature. Since people's perspectives on the world, art, and aesthetics had evolved by this point."¹⁴

It is well known that Uzbek literature has a fully developed narratives, and a large number of works have been produced that satisfy the genre's criteria. The early 20th century saw the formation of the realistic story genre in Uzbek literature. The work of A. Qodiriy initiates this process. One of the earliest instances of the story is found his work "Capricorn".¹⁵

¹² Ma'suma Obidjonova. Genesis of flash fiction genre in the world literature. "International journal on integrated education", 2019

¹³ Ahmedov S., Qosimov B., Qo'chqorov R., Rizayev Sh. Adabiyot (Umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablarining 5-sinfi uchun darslik). I qism. – T.: Sharq, 2011. B. 107-108.

¹⁴ Saydulla Mirzayev. "XX asr O'zbek adabiyoti", "Yangi asr avlodi", Toshkent 2005.

¹⁵ G.Oxunova. Hikoya janri taraqqiyotining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari. -T.: "So'z san'ati xalqaro jurnali", 2021.- bet 70.

“Formal abbreviation, conciseness, content integrity, and brevity are the traditional characteristics of the narrative genre”.¹⁶

Storytelling was developed in antiquity as a form of oral creativity passed down from generation to generation. Through exchanging oral histories, folktales, and epics, people developed storytelling in this way. Oral stories frequently convey heroes, fantastical animals, and moral lessons while also reflecting societal values and beliefs. Despite not having reached its full potential in antiquity, Uzbek storytelling serves as the foundation for storytelling in modern times. In Uzbek storytelling, historical occurrences, cultural customs, and themes of love, loyalty, and respect all play significant roles. The art of storytelling, which reflects the experiences and goals of the Uzbek people, is evolving and changing with the times. With his brief but profound stories, author Abdulla Qahhor significantly influenced the growth of the short story form in Uzbek literature. One thing that sets Abdulla Qahhor apart is his short story writing. In one of his article the writer stated, “I love storytelling at the same time I have always considered it to be the edge of my pen”¹⁷. The main goal of the author’s stories is to uplift and serve people in a moral manner. In his several works author has also tackled the subject of war. In particular, stories about war heroes like “Botirali”, “Asror bobo”, “Xotinlar”, “Sep”, “Ko’k konvert”, “Qizil konvert”.

As Abdulla Qahhor said “The writer does not choose the genre, the genre chooses the writer”¹⁸. Looking at Uzbek literature, we can see that the short story genre is growing after the story genre, and that more authors are researching in this genre. For example, Shukur Xolmirzayev, Nuriddin Egamov, Alloma Hakimova, Nodirabegim Ibragimova, Aziz Nur, Fozil Jo’ra, Muhammadxon Yusupov and others. Authors that started out in the story genre later became well-known for their drabbles. For example, the author O’tkir Hashimov first found great success in the storytelling genre before becoming well-known for his drabbles. Short stories of no more than 100 words, such as “Otalar va bolalar”, “Nasldor Buqa”, “Nosqovoq”, “Aqllilik balosi”, “Gumroh bandalar” and “Tutingan o’g’il” have a particular quick impact on people’s human psyche.

¹⁶ Dilbar Hasanova. O‘zbek hikoyachiligi va uning taraqqiyot yo‘li. “Eurasian Journal Of Academic Research”, 2023

¹⁷ Saydulla Mirzayev. XX asr adabiyoti.-T.: “Ynagi asr avlodi”, 2005.- bet 222

¹⁸ Sh. Absayitova. Zamonaviy o‘zbek hikoyachiligi. “XXI asrda innovatsion texnologiyalar, fan va ta’lim taraqqiyotidagi dolzarb muammolar”, bet 110

According to the author, “I think that in order to create a truly artistic work, to create a work that excites people and gives pleasure to the heart every time it is read again, you need the talent given by God in the first place.”¹⁹

O‘tkir Hoshimov’s drabbles mostly address the topics of parents, society and family. “O‘talar va bolalar” is one of the writer’s drabbles on the theme of family.

Young authors that write in the drabble genre are also present in contemporary Uzbek literature. Abduqayum Yo‘ldoshev, who represents a different field, is among the writers who create drabbles. He has several drabbles including “Muhabbat”, “Azob”, “O‘tinch”, “Ibrat”, “Razolat”, “Ong”, “Baho” and others.

Similar to the authors of literature from the 20th century, today’s young modern writers short stories are valuable for education. Their drabbles mostly discuss love, loyalty and respect. “The main aim of storytelling is to inspire people to do good thing through certain plot”.²⁰

As everyone knows, one of the earliest and most evolving literary genres in the world is the story, especially in English literature. The writings of numerous authors have contributed to the development of world literature, particularly English literature. Famous writers like Mark Twain, William Shakespeare, Jane Austen, James Joyce, William Blake, Geoffrey Chaucer, Charles Dickens and George Eliot made significant contributions to the growth of English literature and subsequently the story genre. William Shakespeare was an English writer who wrote in many genres, particularly comedy and tragedy, even though he is not well known for his stories. His mature works contributed greatly to the development of English literature. As the “father of English literature” Geoffrey Chaucer is regarded as one of the best writers of the Middle Ages in England. One of his most well-known works “Canterbury Tales” is among the most popular pieces of English literature and served as an inspiration for the growth of English storytelling. The main reason is that this work includes 24 stories and critically illuminates the social life, classes, and famous people of that era.

The last great representative of Middle Ages English literature is Geoffrey Chaucer whose works have had a significant influence on the evolution of both the English literary language and English literature. Therefore, he is called the founder of the English language and English realistic literature.²¹

¹⁹ Saydulla Mirzayev. XX Asr O‘zbek Adabiyoti, Toshkent «Yangi asr avlodi» 2005.- bet 397

²⁰ X. Do‘stmuhammedov. Hozirgi o‘zbek hikoyachiligida badiiy tafakkurning yangilanishi.-T.: 2020.

²¹ M.N. Xolbekov. Ingliz adabiyoti klassiklari. – Jizzax.: JDPI, 2014.- bet 7

One of the most well-known writers in the story genre is Charles Dickens. His writings including “Oliver Twist”, “Great Expectations”, and “A tale of Two Cities” had a significant impact on the growth of the English narrative genre.

“Charles Dickens is a creator with an unusual characterization technique otherwise, readers would have forgotten all of his characters, contrary to some critics opinions”²² Samuel Langhorne Clemens is an American writer of short stories who also writes under the pen name Mark Twain. He has a significant impact on the growth of American literature as well as the English story genre. “In addition to representing children’s lives, Mark Twain also captured the common lives of regular people”²³

Another popular German writer is Franz Kafka. His first stories appeared in 1905 in a number of magazines. The works of Franz Kafka have had a significant influence on the literary world and are now regarded as some of the most significant pieces of contemporary literature, stimulating in-depth discussion and deep thought among readers. We may argue that Franz Kafka’s narrative style is intricate. Readers frequently have to make an effort to comprehend Franz Kafka’s writings in order to analyze his stories. “The Trees” is one work with a sophisticated writing style, for instance. In the 1980s, drabbles first appeared in British world literature. Writings of no more than hundred words were not written at this time but short stories contributed to the establishment of this genre.

The first examples of short stories in American literature are found in Washington Irving’s well-known collection “The Sketch of Geoffrey Crayon” published in 1819. Examples of this include “The legend of sleepy hollow” and “Rip Van Winkle.”²⁴ Short story writing became popular after Irving’s writing, and writers from Europe and American wrote about a variety of subjects. Specifically, moral themes were highlighted in the short stories written by renowned author Nathaniel Hawthorne.²⁵

There are many authors of drabbles in English literature, and since this is a relatively new genre, there is still research being done on it. Among the many

²² Berdiyeva Sitora Utkirovna. Charlz Dikkens asarlarida inson ruhiyati tasviri (“Great expectations” (buyuk umidlar) asari misolida) “Innovation science and research international scientific journal volume 1 issue3”, 2023. – bet 68

²³ Ganiyeva Orzigul Xayriddinovna. Mark tven ijodi haqida mulohazalar . “Sifatli ta’lim – taraqqiyot poydevori” mavzusidagi Respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya to’plami 2023-yil 20-apel

²⁴ Margaret Ashmun, Modern short stories . “The Macmillan”. 1914, bet-128

²⁵ <https://americanboard.org/Subjects/english/historical-development-of-the-short-story>

other writers are Lydia Davis, Margaret Atwood, Neil Gaiman, R. Tolkien, K. Clark and others.

Conclusions

In conclusion, literature is a vast and complex field that includes a wide range of genres and approaches. A narrative genre is distinct due to its historical popularity among other features. Beyond adults, young people also like the story genre. We all know that people hear stories from their early years. This makes writing or creating stories in the story genre very fascinating. Readers have not retreated from the narrative genre, which is not surprising, but slightly different-toned short stories have become more and more popular in recent years.

Any reader will be captivated by this new genre's distinctive features. Drabbles in particular are brief pieces that are shorter than one hundred words. The quantity of English and Uzbek authors contributing to this emerging genre is evidently growing daily. Enhancing students' critical thinking ability is one of the primary benefits of drabbles.

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